

THE WAYS OF DEVELOPING PROFESSIONAL SKILLS OF A FUTURE PRIMARY CLASS TEACHER

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Abstract. *This article reveals ways of developing the professional qualities of a future primary school teacher. The motivation for acquiring professional qualifications of a future primary school teacher and the criteria for determining the level of professional training of a teacher and the path of his development are shown.*

Keywords: *qualifications, education, teacher, professional, technology, innovation, development.*

Ensuring the quality of the development of professional knowledge skills of future primary school teachers in world educational and scientific research institutions, modeling and designing the educational process, improving professional training, developing professional qualities and competencies, education scientific researches are being carried out to increase the efficiency of the process, to improve educational and methodological education. In this regard, to teach the mother tongue and prepare for the profession of future primary school teachers on the basis of international qualification requirements, to raise the quality of education to the international level, to determine the professionalism of the future primary school teacher high demands placed on students' activities by modern society, improvement of students' professional ability in the educational process, stimulating possibilities of professional ability, step-by-step study of factors and mechanisms of professional-pedagogical formation attention is being paid.

In recent years, in our republic, the development of professional qualifications of future primary school teachers, the organization of the educational process in primary classes using information technology tools, the development of qualified specialists and professional qualifications, and the creation of legal normative bases for the training of competitive personnel. "Further improvement of the continuing education system, increasing the quality of educational services, continuing the policy of training highly qualified personnel in accordance with the modern needs of the labor market" was defined as an important priority. As a result, pedagogical opportunities for developing the professional skills of future primary school teachers on the basis of pedagogical technologies are increasing. As a result of these scientific studies, innovative pedagogical methods are being developed that help to develop the professional skills of future primary school teachers in the educational process. Strengthening the role of the educational system in raising an intellectually competent student ensures the high quality of primary education and creates a foundation for the introduction of advanced pedagogical and information and communication technologies into the activities of primary school teachers. requires the development of professional skills of future primary school teachers. High demands placed on students' activities by the modern society, improvement of students' professional qualifications in the educational process, stimulating possibilities of professional qualifications, factors and mechanisms of professional-pedagogical formation are being studied step by step.

Pedagogical activity of future elementary school teachers has its own characteristics, which includes, on the one hand, increasing the efficiency of the educational process, and on the other

hand, taking into account a number of limitations. Usually, it occurs due to the peculiarities of psychology and their lack of independent work skills. On the other hand, the need to improve the qualification of the primary school teacher is the primary school, which is designed for the formation of the child's personality, the holistic development of his abilities, the formation of the ability to learn and the desire to learn. Educational programs at this level have the character of integrated courses that lay the foundation for the initial ideas about nature, society, man and his activities. An important means of achieving this goal is the skillful use of educational content and methods, organization of the educational process.

Pedagogical higher education institutions, aimed at the implementation of professional training of future teachers who can effectively carry out educational work, play an important role in solving this task for the educational system of our republic.

The processes of integration in society created the problem of improving the quality of professional training of teachers, especially future primary school teachers, to the employees of the republic's higher education sector. In this regard, it should be noted that in order to carry out his professional activities, the elementary school teacher in the future should have the basic level of professional qualification.

There are at least two views on the origin of the pedagogical term "qualification". According to the first, it means mastering from the English language competence-ability, Latin competences, compenits-meaning capable, knowledgeable in a certain field; has the right to do or decide something, judge something with his knowledge. In the scientific circulation, the term "qualification" was introduced in the defined meaning in the 1960s and 70s. N. Chomsky used the concepts of "communicative competence" in the framework of grammar, D.Haims studied various language abilities in the theory of language teaching.

There are usually three levels of qualifications in scientific literature:

- basic, general culture that goes beyond one's own education and has socio-cultural significance;

- education (at the higher school level - professional) related to educational subjects;

- specially organized within the framework of separate educational subjects.

The nomenclature of qualifications includes socio-economic aspects, which should be considered as a complete definition of factors that serve as a system that forms the content of education within the framework of competence. Today, fundamental changes are observed in the economy, new fields and types of work and processes of updating the content of education have appeared. But considering the qualification only from the socio-economic point of view, "alternative responses of education to the changing demands of the labor market", ignores some important areas of spiritual-ethical, intellectual, economic culture.

A competent approach is understood by many teachers as strengthening the practical direction of education, whose content is formed within the paradigm of the subject.

According to the definition given in the dictionary of vocational education, professional skill is a highly qualified person who can manifest himself in certain forms of professional activity and can adapt to fundamental changes in the market mechanism that manages professional movement and plans career growth. the quality of the employee.

Professional skill or professional qualification - the quality, property or condition of a specialist, his physical, mental and spiritual needs, needs, requirements of a certain profession,

specialization, qualification standards, jointly or separately defining the position of the service held or performed. provides.

The main components of professional qualification are:

- socio-legal competence, that is, having knowledge and skills in the field of mutual cooperation with people and public institutions, as well as a professional communication style;
- personal ability for continuous professional growth and qualification improvement;
- special qualification - ready to independently carry out his professional activity;
- the ability to independently improve one's knowledge and skills in the specialty;
- high competence - the ability to act competently in suddenly difficult conditions.

The unique feature of teachers' professional skills is determined by the uniqueness of the pedagogical profession, its difference from other forms of intellectual work. These features include the following differences:

The systematic nature of pedagogical work requires "immediate analysis and immediate action." For example, during one lesson, the teacher may encounter many difficult situations, and the process diagram is stored in a compressed form when solving them.

An important excellent feature of the teacher's pedagogical activity is the ability to predict the next possibilities of development of reading effects according to the results.

Teachers work individually, and the results of education and training depend on the entire pedagogical team. Sometimes the pedagogical team does not have uniform requirements, and this leads to a decrease in the effectiveness of the pedagogical activity of individual teachers. The effectiveness of pedagogical effects depends on the efforts of each teacher. The professional qualification of a private teacher cannot develop without the appropriate conditions.

Since the teacher's work is complex, it combines special and general professional - psychological and pedagogical knowledge and skills. The teacher's qualification is determined by his ability and ability to perform his professional and pedagogical functions in accordance with the norms and standards accepted by the society. In modern conditions, teachers require a completely different approach to managing their skills. The main directions of this process are the effectiveness of performing professional functions, the situation at work (vacancy, overload, replacement) and the ability to develop oneself.

Psychological-pedagogical and special knowledge are necessary conditions for successful professional activity, methodological knowledge is a condition for pedagogical skills and abilities. Pedagogical skills are a set of pedagogical actions aimed at the implementation of personal development tasks and based on theoretical knowledge. There are several approaches in pedagogy to classify pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skills can be divided into three groups:

1. - Pedagogical tasks
2. - defining and solving various pedagogical tasks.
3. - on the stages of pedagogical process management.

The higher the level of professionalism of the teacher, the more creative he works, and vice versa: the lower level of professionalism is manifested in the repetition of ready-made recommendations.

Pedagogical qualification means that the teacher has a sufficient level of mastering the system of basic educational and educational skills and abilities, which allows him to carry out educational activities at the right level.

Another stage of teacher's professional qualification is pedagogical skills. Pedagogical skill is a high level of excellence that reflects the mastery of methods and methods of applying theory to practice.

The highest level of the teacher's professional qualification includes the promotion and implementation of new, advanced ideas, principles, methods and methods in the process of innovative pedagogic education and a significant increase in their quality. We can see in the works of N.V. Kuzmina, A.S. Makarenko, and A.K. Markov in determining the proportions of professional skill, skill and creativity.

The most important aspect of their theory is:

- to emphasize the need to take into account not only innate characteristics and deposits, but also the conditions of the level of professional skills;

- to allocate all factors to external conditions, work experience and internal work quality.

There are a number of criteria for determining the level of professional training of a teacher:

Objective criteria. Objective criteria in a teacher's work are, first of all, the ability to solve pedagogical requirements.

Subjective criteria - they can know the professional-pedagogical direction, the importance of pedagogical work, its value, and the necessary professional-psychological qualities of a person.

Effective criteria are qualitative changes in the mental development of students.

Procedural criteria - the quality of the teacher's work; use of professional knowledge, skills, techniques, technology in their professional activities.

Normative criteria. It is important for the teacher to master the profession perfectly, to implement the collected things, methodical methods, tools, forms of education and training developed in the field of science and in practice.

Separate - variable criteria. The teacher appreciates such qualities as originality, originality, individuality, personal style. The teacher's professional abilities are formed as a result of his regular work.

According to the main qualifications, a set of subject-specialized qualifications reflecting the specific characteristics of a certain professional activity is understood. Key competencies include:

- Necessary theoretical training.
- Ability to implement acquired knowledge and experience.
- Mastering critical thinking.
- Ability to solve problems depending on the specific situation.

Analysis of the theory and practice of training students of higher educational institutions of pedagogy for future professional activity leads to understanding of the special relevance and importance of the problem of forming the professional skills of future primary school teachers in a rapidly changing world. A broad analysis of literary sources, official materials and documents in various fields of modern science, as well as an analysis of studies dedicated to solving the problem of preparing future teachers for professional pedagogical activity, allows us to come to such a conclusion. The result of these works is the formation of their professional skills.

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